

Operational capabilities of a piloted single jet burner for different hydrogen fuel blends

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In this work, we investigate a single hydrogen jet burner with a premixed pilot injection stage. This burner enables combustion of pure natural gas and hydrogen as well as blends of both fuels. To determine the operational capabilities of this burner different blends of these two fuel types are investigated regarding NO_x emissions and flame shape. For these investigations, the thermal power, the hydrogen content of the fuel blend, the premixing scheme and the flow of the pilot burner are varied.

This study shows that the jet burner concept is suitable for combusting pure hydrogen while maintaining low NO_x emissions over a wide operational range. For the combustion of natural gas, the operational range is narrowed compared to the hydrogen-enriched flames. To stabilize the natural gas flame, a pilot flow injection is used. The effect of this pilot flow on the generation of NO_x is investigated, as well as the flame position.

I. Introduction

The growing demand for mobility, for an increasing living quality, as well as the ongoing technological evolution of modern society stipulates its continuously growing demand for electrical energy. Suitable supply methods, however, need to comply to increasingly strict emission regulations, calling for permanent technological innovations within the power sector. In addition, it is of great importance to surmount the challenges presented by the advancing global climate change by assessing the exploitation of renewable energy sources. The highly intermittent nature of renewable sources such as wind or solar power, however, requires the employment of suitable energy storage techniques as well as the operation of flexible power plants with the ability to seamlessly compensate for power fluctuations in the respective grid. Advantageously, the usage of modern gas turbine technology is well applicable, especially in combination with sustainable, low-carbon, highly hydrogen-enriched fuels, the production of which is powered by renewable sources. In this regard, modern gas turbines allow for highly efficient power generation and, moreover, are optimized for the minimization of pollutant emissions. Currently, gas turbines are mostly operated with fossil fuels as, for instance, natural gas. Here, such fuels are usually combusted in swirl-stabilized combustors, allowing for the combustion of lean premixed air-fuel-mixtures. However, the use of regenerative fuels which rely on a high hydrogen content requires the adaptation of existing combustion processes and, furthermore, the development of novel combustor concepts.

As mentioned above, modern swirl-stabilized combustors, also referred to as swirl burners, achieve very low emission levels while ensuring a safe and reliable operation. Nevertheless, they usually feature complex geometries and, thus, are subjected to rather high-pressure losses. Moreover, swirl burners may be subjected to hydrodynamic instabilities caused, for example, by the precessing vortex core [1, 2]. Additionally, besides aerodynamically stabilizing the flame, swirl burners tend to suffer from flashback induced by vortex breakdown, creating areas of low axial flow velocities [3, 4], as well as from boundary layer flashback along the walls of the combustor and mixing section [5, 6]. For the investigation of this flashback phenomenon, jet burners have been analyzed combusting different types of fuel blends of natural gas and hydrogen [7], and several parameters have been derived. It is known that jet burners rely on a simple turbulent pipe flow comprising a characteristic uniform high momentum flow velocity profile. Due to the resulting high bulk velocities of around 100 m/s, jet flames show a high flashback resistance [8].

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These observed characteristics lead to the appraisal of jet burners being well-suited for the combustion of highly reactive fuels with high burning velocities, such as hydrogen. In this respect, a generic piloted single hydrogen jet burner (POShyDON) has been developed, which allows for an in-depth investigation of the characteristics and emissions of jet flames with high thermal powers up to 150 kW, with a special focus on the emission of NO_x , in order to allow for investigations closer to industrial scale combustors. The burner comprises a pilot stage and a main nozzle for preheated and premixed fuel-air mixtures with a hydrogen content of up to 100 %. The presented design is inspired by the FLOX® burner [9] with the ability of stabilizing flame fronts in single-nozzle burner configurations with or without pilot (as discussed in [8, 10]).

The resulting flame shapes are investigated through camera-based OH^* -chemiluminescence measurements. Besides equivalence ratio and hydrogen content, different thermal power and pilot flow conditions are examined to characterize the jet burner over a broad range of operating conditions, for which also NO_x emissions are measured. Emphasis is put on the impact of the pilot flame on the main flame in terms of varying pilot-fuel-ratio (PFR), ranging from pure air injection (PFR = 0%) to pilot flows with relatively high fuel content (PFR = 15% of the overall fuel content).

The here published description of our work is structured as follows. At first, a description of the experimental setup is given, including the POShyDON-jet burner facility, the applied measurement techniques, and the chosen operating conditions. Subsequently, results regarding flame shape and NO_x emissions are shown for different fuel blends and operating conditions. This paper is concluded by a detailed discussion on the obtained results.

II. Experimental Setup

A. Burner concept

The piloted single hydrogen jet burner (POShyDON) investigated in this study has been designed and tested with thermal powers of up to 150 kW. It is inspired by the FLOX® burner design developed and tested at the DLR [9]. POShyDON can be divided into four different parts: the main flow plenum, the mixing section, the pilot burner, and the combustion chamber, represented by an optical accessible quartz glass tube.

Fig. 1 (a) Schematic side view and (b) front view of the jet-burner POShyDON including gas flows: preheated premixed gases (magenta arrow), fuel (red arrow), preheated air (blue arrow)

The main flow plenum upstream of the converging nozzle is implemented as a simple cylindrical tube. This plenum contains a bent tube that guides the fuel towards the injector in case of technically premixed operating conditions (see Fig. 1a). For these conditions, the fuel is injected in a jet-in-cross-flow configuration into the preheated air through holes that are arranged circumferentially around the injector tip. The fuel-air mixture flows through the mixing section (outlet diameter $D = 34$ mm), the length of which amounts to ten times the outlet diameter, to allow for proper mixing of fuel and air prior to the combustion chamber inlet. To realize perfectly premixed conditions, fuel is injected far upstream of the combustion chamber (see Fig. 2). When the main fuel-air mixture enters the combustion chamber, it interacts with the pilot flow from the pilot burner (see magenta arrows in Fig. 1a and 1b)

To generate a preheated fuel-air flow through the pilot burner, preheated air and cold fuel are mixed far upstream of the pilot burner outlet. The pilot burner outlets are tilted by 60 degrees towards the main flow direction (compare Fig. 1a). With the resulting pilot flow, the root of the main flame is supported, leading to a stabilization of the flame in the upstream region of the combustion chamber.

B. Test rig and measurement techniques

As shown in Fig. 2, POSHyDON (3) is integrated into a test rig which is also utilized for swirl-stabilized combustors in order to investigate thermoacoustic phenomena applying upstream and downstream forcing and microphone arrays. For the present study, the main air is guided through air preheaters (1), which allow for air temperatures at the burner outlet up to 400°C. The fuel-injection lance (2) allows for perfectly premixed conditions by injecting natural gas-hydrogen blends into the microphone tube. For technically, i.e. partially, premixed conditions, the fuel is injected directly into the mixing tube section, positioned at 7.5 nozzle diameters upstream of the combustion chamber inlet (see red arrows in Fig. 1a).

The combustion chamber is represented by a cylindrical quartz glass tube (4) with an inner diameter of 105 mm, allowing for optical access to the flame. This diameter results in an area jump of $A_{\text{chamber}}/A_{\text{jet}} = 9.5$. The optical access is used for OH*-chemiluminescence measurements of the flame using an intensified CCD (ICCD) camera. The chemiluminescence of the OH* radical is generated within the combustion process and appears as ultra-violet light. This characteristic light of a wavelength of around 308 nm is captured by the ICCD camera in combination with an optical band-pass filter. To capture the investigated jet flames, with a length of up to 500 mm for pure natural gas flames, a 50 mm UV lens is utilized. The obtained signal is used as a spatially resolved measure for the heat release rate. To generate (quasi) stationary conditions in the combustor, an orifice (6) is attached at the downstream end of the exhaust tube in order to adjust the acoustic boundary condition.

Fig. 2 Overview of the experimental test stand used for the measurements for this study. More details about the test rig and its features can be found in [11].

C. Emissions measurement

NO_x emissions are measured within the scope of this study for different operating conditions. The gas samples for the emission measurements are taken at position (5) in Fig. 2 via a water-cooled emission probe at several positions along the diameter of the exhaust tube. The nitric oxides are measured on a wet basis by a chemiluminescence detector. This detector is equipped with two channels to measure simultaneously NO_x and NO. Via a separate measurement, the O₂ content is measured to correct the values on a dry basis. This volumetric correction to a dry basis with a reference of 15% O₂ is done in order to compare the results to literature values and is calculated as follows:

$$\text{NO}_{x,\text{standard}} = \text{NO}_{x,\text{ppmvd}} \left(\frac{0.2095 - \text{O}_{2,\text{ref}}}{0.2095 - \text{O}_{2,\text{meas}}} \right) \quad (1)$$

However, this does not account for the volumetric change of the exhaust gas due to the fuel composition, which is

especially relevant for the differing chemical composition of hydrogen. Therefore, we added a further correction as proposed by [12], which accounts for the variation of fuel type. This correction is calculated as follows:

$$\text{NO}_{x,\text{corr}} = \text{NO}_{x,\text{standard}} \left(\frac{\eta + 1 - 0.2095 \theta}{\eta_{\text{ref}} + 1 - 0.2095 \theta_{\text{ref}}} \right), \quad (2)$$

with

$$\eta = \frac{n_{\text{C}}^f}{\theta} \quad \text{and} \quad \theta = \frac{n_{\text{H}}^f}{4} / \text{LHV}^f \quad (3)$$

n_{X}^f denotes the molar amount of the element X in the fuel, whereas η and θ denote fuel-specific parameters, respectively. Since a reference condition is required, the natural gas conditions are assumed with the corresponding Lower Heating Value LHV and η is chosen to be one, as proposed in [12]:

$$\eta_{\text{ref}} = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \theta_{\text{ref}} = \frac{1}{\text{LHV}_{\text{ref}}}. \quad (4)$$

All emission values shown in the following are corrected according to the mentioned procedure.

D. Operating conditions

The air preheating temperature T_{in} is kept constant in this study at 300°C. Fundamental operating conditions varied are the equivalence ratio of pilot flow ϕ_{pilot} and the main flame ϕ_{jet} (0.17 to 0.92). These variations are carried out by varying the thermal power (40 to 120 kW). Also, the jet's bulk velocity is varied between 100 and 140 m/s, corresponding to Reynolds numbers between 60,000 and 95,000, which is achieved through a variation of air mass flow \dot{m}_{air} . Moreover, different premixing modes are tested: perfectly premixed and technically premixed conditions. For the variations of fuel, the thermal power is kept constant, resulting in a variation of equivalence ratio and fuel mass flow; this is done to ensure matching adiabatic flame temperatures.

To archive a constant thermal power, the amount of fuel cannot be constant. Therefore, the correct fuel mass flow is computed as follows, where ζ denotes the mass fraction of the fuel blends and LHV the respective lower heating value of the used gas:

$$\dot{m}_{\text{fuel}} = \frac{P_{\text{th}}}{(1 - \zeta)\text{LHV}_{\text{NG}} + \zeta\text{LHV}_{\text{H}_2}} \quad (5)$$

To characterize the impact of the pilot flames on the main flame, the overall thermal power is kept constant and the fuel and air content in the pilot flow is varied. This variation is described by the pilot fuel ratio (PFR), defined by

$$\text{PFR} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{pilot,fuel}}}{\dot{m}_{\text{pilot,fuel}} + \dot{m}_{\text{premix,fuel}}}. \quad (6)$$

Accordingly, PFR denotes the percentage of the total fuel mass flux fed in the pilot. An analogous definition holds for the pilot-air ratio (PAR):

$$\text{PAR} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{pilot,air}}}{\dot{m}_{\text{pilot,air}} + \dot{m}_{\text{premix,air}}}. \quad (7)$$

This is done to keep the global thermal power and adiabatic flame temperature constant and, thus, to decouple their effect on the NO_x formation.

III. Results

At first, the jet burner is operated without pilot injection under technically premixed conditions and the impact of hydrogen content and thermal power on the flame shape is investigated. Subsequently, the influence of the pilot flow on the flame shape is discussed for perfectly premixed conditions using pure natural gas as fuel. The second part of the results chapter focuses on the effect of the hydrogen content and thermal power on NO_x emissions. Moreover, NO_x emission values are shown for piloted natural gas flames.

Fig. 3 Time-averaged OH* chemiluminescence intensity images describing the mean flame shape of technically premixed flames at $P_{th} = 100$ kW for varying hydrogen mass fraction ζ . The air mass flow is kept constant at $\dot{m}_{air} = 220$ kg/h resulting in a variation in the bulk velocities of the jet of $v_{jet} = 130 - 147$ m/s due to the variation in chemical properties of the fuel composition.

A. Flame shape

The newly developed jet burner (POShyDON) is investigated in order to determine its operational limits. This is done by observing the flame shape as a function of hydrogen content ζ and the thermal power P_{th} . Above this, the influence of different PAR and PFR combinations on the mean flame shape is studied as well.

1. Impact of hydrogen content

The considerably higher flame speed of hydrogen, compared to natural gas, leads to distinct changes of the flame shape. As to be seen in Fig. 3, the pure natural gas flame ($\zeta = 0$) anchors far downstream of the burner outlet around $x/D = 10$.

Increasing the mass fraction of hydrogen to $\zeta = 30\%$ results in a fuel blend which creates a fundamentally different flame. This hydrogen-natural gas flame anchors at the burner outlet and extends in axial direction to $x/D \approx 6$, which is half the length of the 100% natural gas flame. Increasing the hydrogen share further decreases the flame length leading to a concentrated heat release rate close to the burner outlet. For $\zeta > 50\%$, the flame length only slightly decreases such that the pure hydrogen flame ($\zeta = 100\%$) shows an average length of 4.7 D.

2. Impact of thermal power

Another consequence of the higher reactivity and flame speed of hydrogen, in comparison with natural gas, is a significantly different range of thermal powers in which a stable jet flame can occur. This is demonstrated in Fig. 4 which compares pure natural gas ($\zeta = 0$) and hydrogen ($\zeta = 100\%$) jet flames for thermal powers between 40 and 120 kW.

As shown in Fig. 4 on the left, a pure natural gas flame cannot persist for thermal powers $P_{th} < 100$ kW in this burner. For $P_{th} \geq 100$ kW, the flame stabilizes far downstream of the burner outlet leading to extensive flame lengths.

Contrarily, the jet burner offers a larger range of thermal power in which a stable hydrogen jet flame can be achieved (see Fig. 4, right column). For the lower thermal powers ($P_{th} \leq 80$) kW, the flame is detached from the burner outlet. However, the flame is shorter compared to the natural gas cases shown in the left column. Increasing the thermal power to $P_{th} \geq 100$ kW allows for the flame to attach to the burner outlet. Consequently, the flame length further decreases.

Fig. 4 Time-averaged OH* chemiluminescence intensity images describing the mean flame shape of pure natural gas ($\zeta = 0$, left column) and hydrogen ($\zeta = 100\%$, right column) flames. The air mass flow is kept constant at $\dot{m}_{\text{air}} = 220$ kg/h. The bulk velocity of the jet is therefore varied for the different amount and chemical properties of the fuel between $v_{\text{jet}} = 130$ -152 m/s.

3. Impact of pilot flow

Based on time-averaged OH*-intensity images, mean flame shapes are shown for different PAR and PFR values in Fig. 5. This four-by-four matrix shows flames with increasing PFR values in vertical dimension (from bottom to top) and growing PAR values in horizontal dimension (from left to right). The thermal power is kept constant at $P_{\text{th}} = 100$ kW for all cases, which means that global fuel and air mass flow are kept constant resulting in a jet velocity of around 110 m/s. The global equivalence ratio is $\phi = 0.59$ and the natural gas-air mixture is perfectly premixed.

The pilot burner is capable of varying the overall flame shape comparing the flame without any pilot flow (bottom left) with all the other (piloted) flames. Applying fuel only to the pilot burner (column I, row III to I) results in a more upstream-shifted flame which becomes more intense and longer. Adding additional air (increasing PAR) has a similar effect on flame stabilization in the upstream region. However, the momentum increased by the added air causes the flame root to grow in the radial direction. Moreover, the flame length is reduced. Adding air only with PAR = 5% generates a rather triangular flame shape. With additional pilot-fuel, the shape of the flame root becomes bulbous and more intense.

The bottom row of Fig. 5 shows flames with PFR = 0 which means that no fuel is present in the pilot flow. From left to right the amount of air emanating from the pilot burner nozzle into the combustion chamber increases which leads to a distinct upstream shift of the flame. It is rather surprising, that a pure air flow has such a distinct impact on the flame shape and the flame position. Due to the 60 degrees angle in which the pilot flow penetrates the main jet, a certain "bluff-body-effect" sets in. This effect generates favorable flow conditions near the flame root which have a stabilizing effect on the flame.

Increasing the PFR slightly to 6% while keeping PAR at zero, changes the flame shape already clearly (see row III, column I). For this case, only fuel is injected through the pilot burner nozzles, which leads to a locally rich condition around the flame root and rather unmixed conditions. Since PFR is only at 6%, the main flame can still be considered as premixed; however, the pilot is operated rather as a diffusion flame. This pilot flow condition effects an elongated flame which stabilizes close to the main nozzle outlet. Increasing PFR further leads to more heat release rate around the flame root and a slight decrease of the flame length (compare column I in Fig. 5).

The momentum of the pilot flow increases considerably when air is added which has considerable impact on the flame shape. The higher momentum allows the pilot jet to penetrate the main jet in the region of the flame root. As a

result, the flame root is extended in radial direction generating a triangular flame shape with larger angle between jet axis and flame front for PFR equal to 6 and 10 % and PAR > 0 (compare row II and III, column II to IV). For these PFR values, the equivalence ratio of the pilot flow varies between 0.71 and 1.97. Increasing PFR to 14% changes the flame shape considerably. When PAR is larger than zero, the heat release rate is concentrated in the region of the flame root, which takes a rather bulbous shape. Moreover, the length of the flame is clearly decreased. The increased heat release rate at the flame root is a consequence of a very rich pilot flow between equivalence ratios of 1.65 and 2.75 in connection with the increased momentum due to the pilot air.

Fig. 5 Time-averaged OH* chemiluminescence intensity images describing the mean flame shape as a function of PAR and PFR. Global equivalence ratio $\phi = 0.59$, jet velocity $u_{jet} \approx 110$ m/s, thermal power $P_{th} = 100$ kW, perfectly premixed natural gas as fuel

B. NO_x emissions

The emissions of NO_x play a significant role in the design process of a new combustion system and are of critical importance in the context of environmental questions. Moreover, the comparison to the emission levels of similar swirl-stabilized combustors is of high interest in order to motivate fundamental technological changes for future combustion systems.

1. Impact of the hydrogen content

In the following, the hydrogen share is varied, altering its respective mass fraction. Also, the thermal power is varied. The air mass flow and the inlet temperature are kept constant. The pilot burner is not used for the NO_x emissions study presented in this section. As proposed in the previous section, the NO_x values are corrected. The measured results varied over ζ and P_{th} are displayed in Fig. 6.

Over the whole operating range for the ζ variation and the thermal power, the NO_x dry values are below 15 ppm for the POSHyDON burner. This is within the governmental regulations [13], but is also remarkable since no further measures are used to reduce the NO_x formation, such as techniques featuring steam injection. Furthermore, for the case with $P_{th} = 120$ kW, the NO_x emissions are reduced with increasing hydrogen share. This could be caused by two effects; firstly the technical injection with its injection as a jet in cross flow could lead to an overshooting of the injection of fuel in the mixing tube, resulting in fuel touching the wall of the mixing tube. This overshooting could lead to lower mixing quality of fuel and air. Secondly, the higher bulk velocities of the main jet could be beneficial to the flame stability of the hydrogen due to the higher laminar burning velocity of this fuel.

However, this trend of lower NO_x emissions with increasing ζ do not persist for the lower thermal power conditions. For $P_{th} = 100$ kW, the values match the results found in [11] for the same operating conditions with the peak of NO_x being within the varied range. In [11] it was found that the flame length with its resulting residence time has a crucial importance on the NO_x formations and that the peak within the measurement range is physical. For the lower thermal

Fig. 6 Dry low NO_x values corrected with the volumetric change of the fuel composition. The values are plotted over the variation of ζ with varying thermal power P_{th} . The air mass flow is kept constant at $\dot{m}_{air} = 220$ kg/h and an inlet temperature of $T_{in} = 300$ C°. The fuel-air mixture is technically premixed.

power condition $P_{th} < 100$ kW the trend inverses compared to the $P_{th} = 120$ kW-case. Resulting in increasing NO_x with increasing hydrogen share, this could be due to the low equivalence ratios of $\Phi < 0.39$, which results in a detached, highly fluctuating flame. At these thermal powers, a pure natural gas flame cannot be stabilized with the proposed jet burner without the use of a further pilot burner stage.

2. Impact of the pilot flow

In Fig. 7 the NO_x emission values measured, for the same flame configuration as discussed in III.A.3, are depicted in a tile plot where the color indicates the corresponding NO_x value corrected to a dry basis. This plot is arranged in the same way Fig. 5 allowing for a direct comparison to the corresponding flame shapes.

Fig. 7 Influence of the PAR and PFR on the NO_x corrected to a dry basis for perfectly premixed natural gas flames. Global equivalence ratio $\phi = 0.59$, jet velocity $u_{jet} \approx 110$ m/s, thermal power $P_{th} = 100$ kW

In the bottom row, the pilot flow consists of air only which is taken from the main air within a range of zero to 5%. Whereas the lowest NO_x value is reached for the case with no pilot flow at all, the NO_x value slightly increases for $\text{PAR} > 0$. This trend can be explained by the fact that the equivalence ratio of the main jet slightly increases from 0.59 for

PAR = 0 to 0.62 for PAR = 0.05.

Injecting only fuel through the pilot nozzles leads to a distinct increase of NO_x emission (compare column I from bottom to top in Fig. 7). As shown in Fig. 5, the heat release rate is concentrated close to the nozzle which indicates high local temperatures. Moreover, locally fuel-rich regions can form which may lead to hot spots enhancing the thermal NO_x formation path. The maximal NO_x value is measured for PFR = 0.14 with a value above 7 ppm.

Adding air (PAR = 0.03 to 0.05) to the fuel in case of PFR = 0.14 generates a premixed pilot flow with equivalence ratios between 1.97 and 1.18. This premixing reduces the NO_x value clearly because the formation of fuel-rich regions close to the flame root is diminished. However, the highest PFR values appear to be rather unsuitable to achieve low emissions in piloted jet flames in comparison to cases where PFR is smaller than 0.14.

Interestingly, there exists a region of very low NO_x values which are even below values measured for PFR = 0. This region consists of cases with PFR equal to 6 or 10% and PAR = 0.03. Obviously, the stabilizing effect of a well-tuned pilot on the flame can lead to low NO_x emission levels and favorable flame dynamics.

In a different study, a swirl-stabilized combustor has been tested under very similar operating conditions in a similar test rig [14]. The comparison of the quantitative results of the NO_x measurements presented here to those from the swirl combustor shows a very good quantitative agreement. As a result, it can be shown that jet combustors can reach similar NO_x emission levels as swirl combustors for similar operating conditions.

IV. Conclusion

In this experimental study, a newly designed piloted single jet burner is tested for different natural gas-hydrogen blends, varying thermal powers (up to 120 kW) and pilot flow conditions. The performance of the burner is evaluated based on time-averaged OH* chemiluminescence images and NO_x emissions values.

In general, it is shown that jet burners are well-suited to burn fuel blends with high hydrogen contents and even pure hydrogen over a broad operational range. With a higher hydrogen share, the flame becomes more stable and attached to the burner outlet. This results in hydrogen flames being approximately half as long as pure natural gas flames. Due to the high flame stability induced by high shares of hydrogen, a higher variability in thermal power can be achieved compared to pure natural gas jet flames.

The impact of the pilot flow on a pure natural gas flame is distinct and considerably stabilizes the flame. For high shares of hydrogen, the support from the pilot burner is not required since the non-piloted flames are already very stable. Due to the geometrical arrangement of the pilot burner nozzles, the natural gas flame can be stabilized by injecting air only.

Moreover, it is shown over a broad operational range that jet burners can generate low NO_x emission levels. These values depend on the type of fuel injection and for technically premixed conditions, especially on the geometry and quality of the injector. For most operational conditions studied here, single-digit NO_x emission levels are achieved. For the piloted natural gas flames, it is shown that a well-defined pilot flow may decrease the NO_x emissions slightly compared to the non-piloted case.

The single jet burner shown in this work will be used in future studies to investigate the thermoacoustic characteristics of jet flames which are closely connected to the flame dynamics and hydrodynamic instabilities. This phenomenon needs to be further understood for this type of hydrogen(-natural gas) flames in order to build flexible power plants compensating energy provided by renewables.

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